

Dissecting LockBit Ransomware: From Infection to Impact

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Abstract

With Ransomware-as-a-Service (RaaS) drastically lowering the barrier to entry for cybercriminals, ransomware has emerged as one of the most damaging types of cybercrime, with the LockBit ransomware as one of the most widespread and advanced ransomware families. This research combines practical malware analysis with real-world case study evaluations to provide a thorough forensic examination of the LockBit ransomware operation using analysis tools. The analysis revealed key activities including file encryption, ransom note creation, system modifications, and persistence attempts, while highlighting the malware's use of anti-analysis techniques. The study emphasizes the importance of layered forensic approaches, effective detection mechanisms, and proactive mitigation measures such as secure backups and properly configured recovery services to reduce the impact of ransomware attacks on organizational systems.

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1. Introduction

Malware threats present a serious and ever changing risk to business globally, Ransomware being one of the most damaging and disrupting types of cyberattacks, designed to hinder access to the victim’s systems or data, usually by encrypting files and then demanding financial ransom for the restoration (Matthew Kosinski, 2024). Among these threats, **LockBit** ransomware operation has emerged as perhaps the most active and prominent Ransomware-as-a-Service (RaaS) threat actors in recent years (Felipe Castaño, 2025), constantly evolving to avoid discovery and targeting critical infrastructures like healthcare (Alder, 2024).

This report covers a detailed forensic investigation into the LockBit ransomware, where real-world documentations are reviewed with hands-on technical analysis of malware sample is carried out to understand LockBit’s attack methodology, its impacts on victims and the digital artifacts for actionable insights on detection and investigation.

Figure 1 LockBit 3.0 infection chain that uses Cobeacon and KillAV

To learn more about [Malware](#) and [Ransomware](#).

1.1 Aim and Objectives

1.1.1 Aim

The aim of this report is to conduct a comprehensive forensic analysis of the LockBit Ransomware-as-a-service (RaaS) by critically analysing its attack pattern through real-world case studies and carrying out malware analysis.

1.1.2 Objectives

The objectives of the report are as follows:

- To perform a thorough case study review of LockBit ransomware cases in order to understand the ransomware's operational behaviour and impacts.
- To investigate the initial access, payload delivery, lateral movement, encryption procedure, and ransom execution phases of the LockBit attack lifecycle.
- To set up a virtual environment for technical analysis of the malware.
- To evaluate the effects of LockBit ransomware attacks on vital infrastructure industries, with an emphasis on enterprise and hospital settings.
- To obtain useful forensic and detection information that may help in malware investigation, incident response, and upcoming ransomware mitigation tactics.

2. Background

2.1 LockBit Ransomware: Evolution and Operation Model

LockBit ransomware is a sophisticated family of ransomware which functions as Ransomware-as-a-Service (RaaS) platform where the developers create and share customisable malware tools for deployment to their affiliates and get certain profit shares, around 20-30% (Trend Micro staff , 2025). Originated from Russian-speaking cybercriminal forum and first discovered in 2019 as ABCD ransomware, LockBit initially targeted Russian and CIS enterprises using RSA public-key cryptography alongside AES-256 and ChaCha algorithms (MITRE ATTACK, 2023) and the malware quickly spreads globally, affecting industries like government and healthcare. It encrypts file with “.lockbit” extensions, drop ransom letters and creates persistence through self-propagation using SMB attacks (Sangfor Technologies, 2023).

LockBit has evolved through three major versions, each one more powerful and disruptive than the last one:

1. **LockBit 1.0 (2019-2020):** The first version emphasized on speed and dependability and was known for its prompt encryption process and used unique .lockbit extension (Digitalrecovery, 2025).
2. **LockBit 2.0 (2021-2022):** This version was a major upgrade as it added the ability to spread automatically across the Windows network by leveraging the Active Directory settings which allowed a single compromise to cripple the entire enterprise. It also implemented the “double extortion”, meaning it stole the sensitive data before encrypting and threatened to leak it online for payment (Digitalrecovery, 2025).
3. **LockBit 3.0 (2022-Present):** Also known as LockBit Black, this version has anti-analysis and anti-debugging abilities meant to throw off researchers and a bug reward scheme for its own malware with stronger encryption which made LockBit as the most widely used ransomware globally. Additionally, it also allows adjustable features for affiliates to modify attacks (Digitalrecovery, 2025).

2.2 Literature Review

Case Study 1: The LockBit ransomware attack on Boeing Company (2023)

The Boeing cyber-attack is a relevant example in the history of ransomware, showing the increasing sophistication and effects of RaaS operations on major crucial infrastructure companies. In late October 2023, The LockBit group declared they had gained access to Boeing's systems and stolen confidential data, threatening to publish the information online, reportedly demanding USD 200 million extortion payment (Vicens, 2024), which Boeing denied paying after around 43 GB data was published on LockBit's leak site in early November 2023 (Kapko, 2023). The incident affected more than 5,000 accounts, exposing critical data such as Citrix logs, email backups, audit reports and security control documentation (Twingate team, 2024), suggesting exploitation of Citrix Bleed vulnerability (CVE-2023-4966) as initial access vector (FBI, 2023). Despite Boeing claiming that the incident had compromised parts of its **Parts and Distribution Service Division** within the Global Services, but claimed flight safety and operations were not impacted (Vicens, 2024), the scope of data exposure emphasized huge operational and security threats created by ransomware campaigns.

Figure 2 Countdown threatening to leak Boeing's stolen data (securityweek, 2023)

Case Study 2: LockBit's Attack on UK's Royal Mail (2023)

The 2023 Royal Mail ransomware attack highlights the operational and financial consequences of Ransomware-as-a-Service (RaaS) on crucial national infrastructures. In January 2023, the LockBit Black ransomware organization attacked Royal Mail (Page, 2023), encrypting its internal networks and demanding a ransom of up to \$80 million (Stockley, 2023), which the firm refused to pay. The breach hampered worldwide parcel and letter processing for more than six weeks, affecting all 11,500 UK Post Offices (Page, 2023), leaking around 43-45GB of stolen data and costing Royal Mail's main firm, International Distribution Services (IDS) around £10 million and resulted in 6.5% drop in international parcel income during the affected time (Hope, 2023).

The image shows a screenshot of a ransomware website. At the top left is the LockBit 3.0 logo. A red banner reads "LEAKED DATA". Navigation links include "TWITTER", "PRESS ABOUT US", "HOW TO BUY BITCOIN", "AFFILIATE RULES", "CONTACT US", and "MIRRORS". The main content area features a large red countdown timer: "UNTIL FILES 1D18H46M11S PUBLICATION". Below the timer, the deadline is "Deadline: 09 Feb, 2023 03:42:40 UTC". At the bottom, there is a section for "royalmailgroup.com" with a Royal Mail logo and a warning: "ALL AVAILABLE DATA WILL BE PUBLISHED!". Metadata at the bottom indicates the page was "UPLOADED: 06 FEB, 2023 12:55 UTC" and "UPDATED: 07 FEB, 2023 03:44 UTC".

Figure 3 Countdown threatening to leak Royal Mail's stolen data (techcrunch, 2023)

3. Method, Opportunity and Motive

Method

LockBit ransomware attacks often start with Remote Desktop Protocol (RDP) compromises, phishing operations with compromised credentials, or public-facing application vulnerabilities. Once initial access is established, attackers use lateral movement and privilege escalation for activities like collection of system information such as hostnames and domain details, execution of malicious commands and enabling automatic logon for persistence, disable security measures, and spread encrypting software across the network. LockBit's Ransomware-as-a-Service attack strategy involves suspending services, erasing shadow copies and log files, and developing persistence to increase the impact as well as avoid recovery (Oladipupo Akinyemi, 2023).

Tactics, Techniques, and Procedures (TTPs) and Kill Chain: How Does LockBit Breach Networks?

Initial Access	
Technique	Tactic ID
Exploit Public-Facing Applications	T1190
Phishing (Spearphishing Links or Attachments)	T1566
Valid Accounts	T1078

Execution	
Technique	Tactic ID
Command and Scripting Interpreter	T1059
User Execution	T1204

Persistence	
Technique	Tactic ID
Registry Run Keys / Startup Folder	T1547.001
Create Account	T1136

Privilege Escalation	
Technique	Tactic ID
Exploitation for Privilege Escalation	T1068

Defence Evasion	
Technique	Tactic ID
Obfuscated Files or Information	T1027
Disable or Modify Tools	T1562

Credential Access	
Technique	Tactic ID
Credential Dumping	T1003

Lateral Movement	
Technique	Tactic ID
Remote Services (RDP, SMB)	T1021
Internal Spearphishing	T1534

Figure 4 How LockBit Breaches Networks (redpiranha.net)

Opportunity

The LockBit ransomware takes advantage of typical organizational security flaws, such as weak credential management, failed patching, unprotected remote access services, and restricted visibility across company networks. Many businesses run sophisticated configurations with old systems, third-party access, and inadequate monitoring (redpiranha, 2024) which makes it possible for attackers to go unnoticed long enough to escalate privileges and steal data. In industries where downtime and data exposure greatly increase pressure to comply with ransom demands, such as manufacturing, logistics and healthcare, the Ransomware-as-a-Service (RaaS) model further expands opportunity by allowing affiliates to exploit these widespread vulnerabilities at huge amount (FBI, 2023).

Motive

The major motive of LockBit ransomware operations is financial gain, with the group aiming to maximize profit through extensive extortion. By using the RaaS model, LockBit makes it possible for affiliate to launch attacks and split the ransomware money with developers, around 20-30% to LockBit operators after taking initial fee for access, resulting in a successful and long-lasting criminal operation (Trend Micro staff , 2025). The group uses double extortion techniques in order to put more operational and psychological pressure on the victim, compelling them to pay double in which the stolen data is threatened with public release in addition to the data encryption. Besides financial gain, maintaining reputation among the cybercriminal network and proving its technical efficiency is also one of the motives (Legorano, 2024).

4. Critical Forensic Analysis

4.1 Lab Setup

Executing ransomware samples directly on a host system presents considerable security hazards therefore, a secure virtual testing environment was set up for analysis. Inside Windows 10 all the necessary tools such as Process Monitor, Process Explorer, Regshot, Autoruns, Wireshark and Detect It Easy (Die) were installed.

Figure 5 Setting Host Only Network

Guest Isolation mode was activated and drag and drop and copy and paste was isolated as to prevent malware from escaping via the VM clipboard.

Figure 6 Enabling Guest Isolation

4.2 LockBit Demonstration and Analysis

The sample malware was obtained from the website:

<https://bazaar.abuse.ch/browse.php?search=tag%3A+LockBit>

Date (UTC)	SHA256 hash	Type	Signature	Tags	Reporter	DL
2025-12-19 11:59	cd6d48db36adc645d60d...	dll	BlackMatter	BlackMatter dll lockbit	NDA0E	
2025-12-19 11:59	e90bd4ffc09f362b480fd8...	exe	BlackMatter	BlackMatter exe lockbit	NDA0E	
2025-12-19 11:58	a61687dca6e71baa451a...	exe	LockBit	BlackMatter exe lockbit	NDA0E	
2025-12-06 17:31	637be4d4df565ad9299b...	exe	LockBit	exe lockbit	jurroots	
2025-12-01 12:07	032690f113289d50b672f...	exe	LockBit	exe github-vixtamp lockbit	skocherhan	
2025-11-09 08:51	bfe5a9f95eabd077326eb...	vbs	LockBit	lockbit Nebula NebulaDropper vbs	Anonymous	
2025-10-19 22:25	7df420f9c3846e357c666...	exe	BlackMatter	BlackMatter exe lockbit	nickkuechel	
2025-09-20 01:27	4dc06ecee904b9165fa69...	elf	LockBit	elf linux lockbit lockbit 5.0 lockbit5 Ransomware	Lacorte1337	
2025-09-20 01:27	90b06f07eb75045ea3d4...	elf	LockBit	elf ESX lockbit lockbit5 Ransomware	Lacorte1337	
2025-09-20 01:26	180e93a091f8ab584a827...	exe	LockBit	chuongdong exe lockbit lockbit 5.0 lockbit5 signed	Lacorte1337	
2025-09-15 06:07	7ea5afbc166c4e23498aa...	exe	LockBit	exe lockbit lockbit5 Ransomware signed	Neiki	
2025-08-12 20:54	374f9df39b92cccca8a9...	exe	BlackMatter	BlackMatter exe lockbit Ransomware	AntiSkidding	

Figure 7 Malware sample from MalwareBazaar

Browse / Malware sample

MalwareBazaar Database

You are currently viewing the MalwareBazaar entry for SHA256 0ec87a7f943ab72d08aeb957d33dd348ab7cf45052ab7a31bccc33ff7a095837. While MalwareBazaar tries to identify whether the sample provided is malicious or not, there is no guarantee that a sample in MalwareBazaar is malicious.

Database Entry

Intelligence **11** | IOCs | YARA **1** | File information | Comments | Actions

Figure 8 Malware Sample

Before executing the malware, some dummy files were created for further observation.

Figure 9 Dummy files

The real time threat and virus monitoring system of the VM was disabled before executing the malware. This ensured the smooth execution of the malware.

Figure 10 Threat and virus protection off

Here, the registry value “**identifier**” was removed from Windows HKLM hive to ensure the malware does not detect virtualized environments as modern ransomware families like LockBit includes anti-analysis and anti-VM checks to avoid execution in sandboxed or virtual environments used by researchers.

Figure 11 Deleting Identifier from Windows hive

After further investigation, a **Lockbit.exe** process was observed running multiple sub processes which showed a high CPU usage, indicating active encryption.

Figure 14 Process Explorer with Lockbit.exe

Here, it was observed that the malware successfully infected the host. A file named Lockbit.zip with LockBit icon was observed along with the wallpaper being changed to LockBit Black. A random file was also created on the desktop.

Figure 15 Wallpaper changed due to infection

When the **fu28x4MDV.README.txt** file was accessed, the following ransom note was found.

Figure 16 LockBit ransom note

It was observed that all the dummy files were encrypted and weren't accessible anymore.

Figure 17 Encrypted dummy files

Figure 18 File contents changed to gibbrish

In process monitor application, the Disk I/O was observed to be greater than usual which indicated the malware was actively running.

Figure 21 Disk and Network monitoring

In the Registry Editor, the wallpaper used by LockBit was observed.

Figure 22 Registry Explorer wallpaper

Regshot, a comparison tool, was used to compare the changes in the processes after the malware was executed. It was observed that the malware had executed a process with the Unicode

```

“53 41 43 50 01 00 00 00 00 00 00 00 07 00 00 00 28 00 00 00 FA 02 1B 00 93 B2 1B
00 01 00 00 00 00 00 00 00 00 00 00 0A 00 21 00 00 50 BB 64 ED DD AC D5 01 00 00
00 00 00 00 00 00 05 00 00 00 10 00 00 00 00 00 00 00 00 00 00 00 00 00 00 00
00 00 02 00 00 00 28 00 00 00 00 00 00 00 00 00 40 00 00 00 00 00 00 00 00 00
00 00 00 00 00 00 25 2C 09 00 00 00 00 00 01 00 00 00 01 00 00 00”

```

which decoded into fu28x4MDV.README.txt. This showed the malware successfully creating a ransom note file with the discussed process.

Figure 23 Regshot with the Unicode

Additionally, the sample was also run through Any.run sandbox and the following setting was set.

Figure 24 Any.run settings

It was observed that the result showed malicious activity but the sample did not run as expected. This is due to the sophisticated nature of the ransomware families like LockBit as they detect the sandboxed environment and do not run.

Figure 25 Any.run results showing malicious activity

Several analysis tools, including Process Monitor, Registry Explorer, Autoruns, and Regshot, were used in this forensic analysis to closely monitor system, registry, and persistence-related behaviours. These results made it possible to have a stronger understanding of how systematic changes take place and how malicious activities try to stay persistent.

5. Result and Evaluation

The LockBit ransomware activities were monitored using a mix of static and dynamic techniques. Regshot was used to compare the system and registry states before and following execution, while Process Monitor and Process Explorer were utilized to track real process, file, and system activity. An organized analysis of the malware's effects on the operating system was done using Autoruns and Registry Explorer, which enabled the detection of persistence-related artifacts and configuration alterations.

The final results revealed that the malware carried out its main ransomware operations and executed correctly. A complete infection cycle was demonstrated through the encryption of user-generated data, the creation of a ransom letter, and changes to the desktop wallpaper. During execution, there was increased CPU and disk I/O activity, which is linked to active encryption processes. Autoruns indicated suspicious start-up-related entries that suggested attempted persistence, even though some entries were non-functional. Registry analysis showed alterations pertaining to system appearance and application behaviour.

The analysis reveals that the technologies used were successful in identifying the LockBit ransomware's primary characteristics, such as encryption activity, system alteration, and persistence attempts. Even though some sophisticated methods, like manipulating backup or recovery services, were not seen in this research, the inquiry nonetheless offered valuable forensic insight into the malware's operational impact within the virtualized environment.

Prevention:

Some of the mitigation techniques for ransomware threats such as LockBit are as follows:

- Keep backups of important data on a regular basis, ideally kept offline or on network segments that are not directly accessible from the primary system.
- To ensure backup snapshots are available in the event of data loss, make sure Volume Shadow Copy Service (VSS) is enabled and configured correctly.
- To guard against known vulnerabilities, patch systems and apps on a regular basis.
- Use the least privilege principle and network segmentation to reduce the impact of an infection.
- Use log analysis, endpoint monitoring, and intrusion detection to find unusual activity early.

6. Conclusion

A thorough understanding of the LockBit ransomware's operational methods, such as file encryption, ransom note creation, and system alteration, has been made possible by the forensic research. The malware's actions showed how ransomware, even in a controlled virtual environment, uses registry modifications and system processes to gain persistence and interfere with regular activities.

The combination of analysis tools such as Process Monitor, Regshot, Autoruns, and Registry Explorer, were used to accurately observe and connect the malware's actions with the resulting system artifacts. While certain anti-analysis techniques limited the full execution of some functions, the analysis effectively identified important behavioral patterns and relevant results for detection and investigation.

Overall, the study emphasizes how important it is to take proactive mitigation steps, like implementing strict access rules, updating regularly, and keeping safe backups. Organizational resilience against ransomware attacks can be further strengthened by making sure VSS and other recovery techniques are installed correctly. This investigation shows how important thorough forensic methods are for comprehending ransomware risks and assisting with successful prevention and response plans.

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8. Appendix

8.1 Malware

Malware, short for malicious software, is any program that has been deliberately created to interrupt operations, disrupt systems, steal data, or gain unauthorized access to computers and networks. Malware includes viruses, worms, trojans, spyware, adware, and ransomware, all of which serve different malicious objectives. Malware is still one of the most common cyber security risks because of its ability to exploit both technical and human errors (malwarebytes, 2024).

Malware threats have grown in size, sophistication, and organization in recent years, progressing from individual attacks to professionally handled cybercriminal operations. Modern malware operations commonly include automation, encryption, and flexible designs, allowing attackers to quickly customize payloads and avoid detection. According to ENISA reports, malware is increasingly being deployed via phishing, exploitation of public-facing applications, and the abuse of legal credentials, indicating a move toward stealthier and more persistent attack techniques (ENISA, 2022).

Figure 26 Types of Malware

8.2 Ransomware

Ransomware is a type of malware which prevents the user to access the system or data, mainly through encryption and demanding ransom for restoration. Modern ransomware attacks often integrate data exfiltration where sensitive data and information are stolen and threatened to be made public if the ransom amount is not paid. Increasing use of double-extortion method has further fuelled the outbreak of ransomware attacks, making them one of the most disruptive cyber threats organizations face today (malwarebytes, 2024).

Figure 27 Workflow of ransomware